

EFFECT OF FIBER CONFIGURATION ON TRANSVERSE CRACKING OF PLAIN WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITES UNDER IN-PLANE TENSILE LOADING

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SUMMARY: This paper described the effect of fiber configuration such as fiber crimping and cross sectional geometry of fiber bundle on mechanical properties and damage accumulation of plain woven composite under in-plane loading. In the plain weave used, fiber crimping and cross sectional geometry were different between warp and weft direction. As a result of experiment, mechanical properties were affected by the fiber configuration. Moreover, propagation behavior of transverse crack in the warp specimen was obviously different from the weft specimen. This tendency was confirmed by finite element analysis. The difference in propagation of transverse crack was caused by tensile stress distribution resulted from the fiber configuration.

KEYWORDS: Fiber configuration, Transverse crack, Plain woven fabric, In-situ observation, FEM analysis

INTRODUCTION

Woven fabric composites have been increasingly used for various applications because of not only their high mechanical performances, but also excellent handling ability which contributes to reduce fabrication cost. On the other hand, fiber rich and resin rich regions are inherently formed due to the heterogeneity of woven fabric. Hence various microscopic damages occur such as matrix crack, transverse crack, fiber rupture and delamination [1-2], so that woven fabric composites reveal complicated fracture mechanism. The catastrophic failure of woven fabric composites is resulted from accumulation of these micro damages. Therefore to clarify the mechanism of micro damage initiation is significantly important [3-4].

In the woven fabric composites, onset of the micro damages is affected by both stress distribution and material properties considering not only fiber and matrix, but also fiber/matrix interface. The stress distribution inside of the composites depends on configurations of the fiber bundles such as fiber crimping caused by interlacing, cross sectional geometry of fiber bundle and distance between fiber bundles which align in parallel. Thus, these fiber configurations much influence on mechanical characteristics of woven fabric. Recently, some numerical studies on prediction of elastic and plastic characteristics such as degradation of stiffness, change in Poisson's ratio and deformation behavior of woven fabric model considering various fiber architectures have been reported. However, the

numerical models used are based on the ideal woven geometry in these issues, and the report has been restricted almost exclusively to the macroscopic properties and there was no one associating initiation and propagation mechanisms of micro damage based on precise experimental observation with the fiber configuration.

In this study, the effect of fiber configuration on the onset and propagation behavior of plain woven composite under in-plane loading was investigated. The mechanical properties of plain woven composite with different fiber configuration in terms of fiber crimping and cross sectional geometry for fiber bundle was experimentally and analytically discussed.

EXPERIMENT

Materials and Specimen

Plain glass weave (WEA7628, Nitto Boseki Co., Ltd.) which is applied into the electric circuit board was used as reinforcements. The diameter of single filament and fineness of fiber bundle within the fabric were $9\mu\text{m}$ diameter and 400 filaments, respectively. In the plain weave used, the number of warp and weft fiber bundles per inch was 44 and 33, respectively. Figure 1 shows optical micrographs of 1-ply plain woven fabric composite in cross sectional view. The warp and weft fiber bundles are in parallel with the pictures in Fig. 1(a) and (b), respectively. Because of larger density for warp fiber bundle, the distance between each warp fiber bundle was shorter than the distance between each weft fiber bundles. The fiber configuration such as fiber crimping and cross sectional geometry can quantitatively be expressed as crimp ratio and aspect ratio as shown in Fig. 2, respectively. Both crimp ratio and aspect ratio were higher for the warp fiber bundle than those for the weft fiber bundle as listed in Table 1.

As matrix resin, vinyl ester (RIPOXY R806, Showa High polymer, Co., Ltd.) was used. 0.7 phr of methyl-ethyl-ketone-peroxide (Permeck N, Nihon Yushi Co., Ltd.) was used as initiator of polymerization of the matrix. 1ply plain woven composite was fabricated by hand-lay-up technique. The matrix resin was cured at room temperature for 48 hours and post cured at $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 2 hours. Thickness of the sheet was 0.2 mm and theoretical averaged fiber volume fraction was 47 %. Two kinds of tensile specimen in which warp and weft directions of the fabric was corresponded to longitudinal direction of the specimen were prepared. Schematic drawing of tensile specimen is shown in Fig. 3. Length and width of the specimen were 200 mm and 20 mm, respectively. Aluminum plate with 1.0 mm thickness was bonded at the edges. Strain gage with 5 mm of measure length (KFG-5-120-C1-11, KYOWA Electric Co., Ltd.) was put on the center of the specimen.

Fig. 1 Cross-sectional view of 1ply plain woven composite of (a) warp and (b) weft fiber bundles aligning in parallel of this paper.

Fig. 2 Definition of woven parameters.

Fig. 3 Schematic drawing of tensile specimen.

Table1 Woven parameters of each fiber

Fiber bundle	Crimp ratio	Aspect ratio
Warp	0.174	0.154
Weft	0.112	0.143

Tensile Test and Measurement of Acoustic Emission

Tensile test was performed by using INSTRON testing machine (Type 4206, INSTRON Japan, Co., Ltd.) with constant cross-head speed of 1.0 mm/min. at room temperature. The load and strain data were gathered as digital information by using personal computer. In order to identify the initiation of micro fracture during tensile test, monitoring of acoustic emission (AE) was carried out. The AE sensor resonating with 150 kHz was fastened at the center of specimen using grease and plastic tape. The AE data was analyzed by AE equipment (SPARTAN 3000, Physical Acoustic Corporation Co., Ltd.). The gains of pre-amplifier and main amplifier were 40 dB and 60dB, respectively, and threshold of elastic wave was 30dB.

In-situ Observation of Micro Fracture

In order to investigate the effect of fiber configuration on the initiation and propagation of micro fracture, in-situ observation of tensile test was performed. Figure 4 shows the out of view of testing equipments. For tensile test, small tensile testing machine (Minimat 2000, Rheometric Scientific FE Japan, Co., Ltd.) was used. This machine was placed on the sample stage of optical microscope (BX50, Olympus Corporation). The micrographs of damage initiation and propagation were recorded by using digital camera (CAMEDIA C3030zoom, Olympus Corporation).

Fig. 4 Overview of testing apparatus of in situ observation.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Mechanical Properties

Tensile stress-strain curve for the warp and weft specimens is shown in Fig. 5. Stress linearly increased with increasing strain at initial stage of test, and stiffness gradually decreased over than middle stage for both specimens. Experimental results are listed in Table 2. Modulus and strength of the warp specimen were higher than those of the weft specimen because the fiber content of the warp specimen was higher than that of the weft specimen.

Tensile stress-displacement curve and cumulative AE event-displacement curve for warp and weft specimens are shown in Fig. 6. At elastic region, AE event was not detected. In the warp specimen, AE event was generated at 68MPa. On the other hand, AE event was generated at 57MPa in case of the weft specimen. Because the generation of AE was recognized as the micro damage initiation, AE generating stress, σ_{AE} , was defined as the stress where AE events were generated. Hence, AE generating strain, ε_{AE} , corresponding to σ_{AE} could be obtained from stress-strain curve. Table 2 also lists AE generating stress and strain. Both σ_{AE} and ε_{AE} were higher for the warp specimen than those for the weft specimen.

Fiber content of the warp specimen was larger by 33% than that of the weft specimen, but the modulus, strength and AE generating stress were not proposed to the fiber content. This was because the crimp ratio of longitudinal fiber bundle in the warp specimen was larger than that in the weft specimen.

Fig. 5 Tensile stress-strain curve.

Fig. 6 Tensile stress-displacement curve and cumulative AE events-displacement curve.

Table 2 Experimental results.

	Modulus, E (GPa)	Strength, σ_U (MPa)	AE generating stress, σ_{AE} (MPa)	AE generating strain, ε_{AE} (%)
Warp	20.0	306	67.9	0.312
Weft	18.4	278	56.6	0.269

In-situ Observation

Figure 7 shows the optical micrographs of in-situ observation during tensile test. The onset of transverse crack for the warp and weft specimens were confirmed at 230MPa and 150MPa stresses, respectively. The transverse crack increased and propagated with increasing stress.

Interestingly, the weft specimen clearly showed a single transverse crack in one fiber bundle, although the warp specimen showed several cracks in one fiber bundle.

It was considered that this difference was caused by the difference in the crimp ratio and aspect ratio. Figure 8 shows the mechanism for onset of transverse crack in intersection of woven composite in case of both the warp and weft specimens. The longitudinal fiber bundles tended to be straightened under in-plane tensile loading, and this phenomenon caused flexural deformation of perpendicular fiber bundle in each intersection. As a result, the perpendicular fiber bundles were subjected to tensile stress. Because crimp ratio and aspect ratio of the warp specimen were different from the weft specimen, it was considered that tensile stress distribution state in perpendicular fiber bundle of these specimens were difference. Therefore it was considered that micro damage aspect of the warp specimen was different from that of the weft specimen.

Fig. 7 In-situ observation during tensile test in (a) warp and (b) weft direction loading.

Fig. 8 Mechanism for onset of transverse crack in case of (a) Warp and (b) Weft specimens.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Numerical Model and Boundary Conditions

In order to discuss the effect of fiber configurations on micro damage aspect, numerical analysis based on finite element method (FEM) was carried out. Figure 9 shows analytical model of the intersection for (a) warp specimen and (b) weft specimen. The geometrical parameters such as distance between fiber bundles, small and large diameter of the fiber bundle and fiber crimping for both models were based on actual one as listed in Table 1. 2-D plain strain element was used for construction of the model. This model consisted of longitudinal fiber element, perpendicular fiber element and matrix resin element. It was noted that this model expressed only one cross section of actual specimen, and the effect of interaction of interlacing fiber on the stress distribution could not be considered. But the loading condition of experiment was uni-axial loading, so that we considered that the effect of interlacing fiber on mechanical performance could not be ignored.

Table 3 lists the material constants used for each element. The element of longitudinal fiber bundle was assumed as unidirectional composite. Hence, the elastic moduli (longitudinal, transverse and shear) were calculated by following equations (1), (2) and (3). The element for perpendicular fiber bundle was assumed as isotropic material, and modulus was calculated by equation (2). Fiber volume fraction of the longitudinal and perpendicular elements was assumed as 70%.

Boundary condition was indicated in Fig. 9. For both models, the displacement in longitudinal direction of all nodes on edge AB was fixed. For both edge AB and CD, the displacement in out-of-plane direction of the node at center of longitudinal fiber was fixed. 1.0 mm displacement was applied to all nodes on the edge CD. The analysis conducted in this study was linear analysis because the purpose was to understand effect of fiber configuration on the stress distribution at elastic region.

Fig. 9 2D FEM models and boundary conditions for (a) Warp and (b) Weft models.

Table 3 Material constants in case of 2D FEM analysis.

Type of material	Modulus E_L (GPa)	Modulus E_T (GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν_L (-)	Poisson's ratio ν_T (-)	Shear modulus G (GPa)
Longitudinal fiber bundle	52.8	18.5	0.31	0.10	6.83
Perpendicular fiber bundle	18.5		0.3		7.12
Matrix resin	3.4		0.3		1.31

Results

Figure 10 shows magnified deformation state for both models subjected to 0.1 % tensile strain. It was found that the longitudinal fiber bundle was straightened when tensile load was subjected. As a result, the intersection was deformed in out-of-plane direction under only in-plane loading. Similar analytical results on the deformation of intersection in out-of-plane direction resulted from its asymmetrical structure were reported by Whitcomb et al. [5]. Obviously, intersection of the warp model was deformed in out-of-plane direction by four times than the weft model because the crimp ratio of longitudinal fiber bundle in the warp model was larger than that in the weft model.

The distributions of vertical stress in loading direction along the symmetrical axis of perpendicular fiber bundle for both models are shown in Fig. 11. The value of vertical axis of this figure was normalized by the minimum value of each model. Because the degree of flexural deformation for the warp model was large, the difference in tensile stress between both edges for the warp model was larger than that for the weft model. Figure 12 shows vertical stress distributions along surface of the perpendicular fiber bundle for both models. Similarly, the value of vertical axis of this figure was normalized by minimum value. Interestingly, it was found that the stress distribution state of the warp model was different from that of the weft model. In case of the warp model, tensile stress was maximized at the center of the perpendicular fiber bundle. On the other hand, high tensile stress was uniformly distributed along the surface of perpendicular fiber bundle in case of the weft model.

Fig. 10 Deformation states of (a) Warp and (b) Weft models.

Fig. 11 Normalized tensile stress distribution along the symmetrical axis of perpendicular fiber bundle.

Fig. 12 Normalized tensile stress distribution along the outside of perpendicular fiber bundle.

From the numerical analysis, it was confirmed that fiber configuration affected tensile stress distribution in perpendicular fiber bundle. This result was agreed with the experimental result as shown in Fig. 7 and 8. The warp specimen showed single transverse crack in a perpendicular fiber bundle because the tensile stress was locally maximized at center of the perpendicular fiber bundle. On the other hand, multiple transverse crack occurred in the weft specimen because high tensile stress was distributed at wide region of the perpendicular fiber bundle.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the effect of fiber configuration on the onset and propagation behavior of plain woven composite under in-plane loading was investigated. Fiber crimping affected mechanical properties such as modulus, strength and AE generating stress. In addition, the transverse crack propagation behavior was different between the warp and weft specimen. From FEM analysis, the difference in the propagation behavior of transverse crack was caused by the difference in tensile stress distribution. Consequently, the effect of fiber configuration on the mechanical properties and damage propagation has to be taken into account for structural design using the woven composite

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